

Desarrollo de un proyecto divulgativo interactivo
para la formación en la documentación del
contenido audiovisual.

**TFG del grado en Gestión de Información y
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Efecto/animación de desplazamiento de tarjetas
apiladas - página del código

<https://makedreamwebsite.com/make-this-stacked-card-scrolling-effect-animation-in-elementor/>

Fragmento de código CSS para el efecto de desplazamiento de tarjetas
apiladas:

```
selector{
  --card-scroll-height: 400;
  --card-rotate: 12;
}
selector .mdw-active-card{
  transform: translateY(-100vh) rotate(-60deg) !important;
  transition:1s;
  visibility: hidden;
  transform-origin: bottom left;
}
selector > .e-con,
selector > .e-container,
selector > .e-con-inner > .e-con,
selector > .e-con-inner > .e-container{
  position: sticky;
  top:0;
}
```

Fragmento de código JavaScript para el efecto de desplazamiento de tarjetas apiladas:

```
<script src="https://code.jquery.com/jquery-3.5.1.min.js"></script>
<script>

if(!MDWNonce100){

var MDWNonce100 = true

$(document).ready(function() {

var previousScrollTop = [],
cards = [],
cardScrollHeight = [],
cardRotate = [],
cardContainer = [],
stickyTop = [],
stickyCon = []

// Sliding crads on scroll
function cardSlideUp(){

$('.mdw-stacked-card-area').each(function(i){

var $this = $(this),
scrollTop = $(document).scrollTop(),
cardAreaTop = $this.offset().top,
index = Math.floor((scrollTop - cardAreaTop - stickyTop[i]) /
cardScrollHeight[i]),
totalCards = cards[i].length

cards[i].removeClass('mdw-active-card')
cards[i].each(function(j){
if( j <= index ) {
$this.addClass('mdw-active-card')
}
if(index >= -1 && index < totalCards - 1){
$this.css({
'transform': `rotate(${ -1*j*cardRotate[i] +
(index+1)*cardRotate[i] }deg)`
})
}
})

previousScrollTop[i] = scrollTop
})

}

function setValues(){
```

```

$('.mdw-stacked-card-area').each(function(i) {

    var $this = $(this)

    stickyTop[i] = 0

    if(stickyCon[i].outerHeight() > $(window).height()){
        stickyTop[i] = cardContainer[i].offset().top -
stickyCon[i].offset().top - $(window).height()/2
    }
    stickyCon[i].css('top', -1*stickyTop[i])

    cardScrollHeight[i] = $this.css('--card-scroll-height') ?
parseInt($this.css('--card-scroll-height').trim()) : 400
    cardRotate[i] = $this.css('--card-rotate') ?
parseInt($this.css('--card-rotate').trim()) : 9

    // Rotating cards

    cards[i].each(function(j) {
        $(this).css({
            'transform': `rotate(-${j * cardRotate[i]}deg)`,
            'z-index': cards[i].length - j
        })
    })

    // Card area height

    $this.css('height', stickyCon[i].outerHeight() +
((cards[i].length - 1) * cardScrollHeight[i]) + 'px' )
})

}

$(document).on('scroll', cardSlideUp)
$(window).on('resize', function(){
    setValues()
    cardSlideUp()
})

function init(){

$('.mdw-stacked-card-area').each(function(i) {

    var $this = $(this)

    cards[i] = $this.find('.mdw-stacked-cards > .e-con, .mdw-
stacked-cards > .e-container, .mdw-stacked-cards > .e-con-inner >
.e-con, .mdw-stacked-cards > .e-con-inner > .e-container')

```

```
    stickyCon[i] = $this.children('.e-con, .e-container').eq(0)

    stickyCon[i].parents().each(function(){
        if( !$this.is('html') ){ $this.css('overflow',
'visible') }
    })

    previousScrollTop[i] = $(document).scrollTop()
    cardContainer[i] = $this.find('.mdw-stacked-cards')
})

setValues()
cardSlideUp()

}

init()

})
}
</script>
```